

Epidemiology and Risk Factors of Recurrent Shoulder Dislocation Among Young Athletes in Iraq

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Abstract

Recurrent shoulder dislocation (RSD) is an orthopedic issue that is substantially prevalent among youth athletes and has a high rate of morbidity and potential for future long-term disability. To determine the epidemiology and risk factors for RSD among young Iraqi athletes, 285 athletes aged 16-35 years who experienced RSD and presented to a Private Hospital over two years (January 2022 - December 2023) were examined in this cross-sectional study. Information regarding demographic characteristics, clinical presentation, sports participation, and potential risk factors was collected via standardized questionnaires and clinical evaluations. Using multivariate logistic regression analysis, independent predictors were determined. The mean age of study participants was 24.3 ± 6.5 years, with 78.9% being male. The results demonstrate that participation in contact sports is a statistically significant predictor of developing RSD (OR: 3.42, 95% CI: 2.15-5.44), along with prior shoulder injury (OR: 4.78, 95% CI: 2.89-7.91) and increased generalised ligamentous laxity (OR: 2.94, 95% CI: 1.67-5.18). The overall recurrence rate for RSD was determined to be 62.1% within two years of the initial shoulder dislocation. Young athletes who sustain their first dislocation at an earlier age have a decreased risk of recurrence compared to older athletes ($r = -0.547$, $p < 0.001$). Findings of this study provide new insights into the epidemiology of RSD in the Iraqi youth athlete population and the need for identifying risk factors early to implement preventative measures and develop appropriate management strategies.

Introduction

Shoulder dislocation is one of the most frequently dislocated joints in human beings. It represents approximately 50% of all major joint dislocations treated at all emergency departments across the planet. Anteriorly dislocated shoulders are the most common (95-98% of all cases), while posteriorly and inferiorly dislocated shoulders can occur but are less frequent overall, as these dislocation types are most common in association with specific types of traumatic events or underlying diseases of the neuromuscular system [1].

Shoulder dislocations (especially RSD) are a major clinical issue due to their impact on the ability to

perform athletically or quality of life. The RSD is defined as having had two (2) or more episodes of symptomatic glenohumeral instability that need either manual or surgical reduction. From epidemiological data it is estimated that between 50%-60% of patients who have their first anterior shoulder dislocation will experience at least one (1) additional dislocation within five (5) years after their original episode. Also, it has been shown through research that recurrence rates are much higher in the younger population than older population [3-4]. The risk of experiencing an RSD is highest for athletes that are under the age of 30, with many studies indicating that the recurrence rate for

More Information

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younger athletes involved in contact or overhead sports can be as high as 80% [5].

Young athletes are a unique population that is at high risk for having an RSD due to the combination of many biomechanical/physiological factors. For example, they typically present with significantly more skeletal mobility than the average adult, and experience less than average ligamentous support at their joints due to their youthfulness and high demands placed on their bodies through competitive athletic activity. This creates a biomechanically favourable environment for injury recurrence. In general, Athletes tend to return to sports early after the first episode of dislocation even though they may not have developed the necessary neuromuscular control or healed structurally, leaving them susceptible to re-injury [6,7]. The mechanism of re-dislocation (RSD) in athletes is significantly different from that of non-athletes as traumatic recurrences are more prevalent in the athlete population, while atraumatic and microtraumatic recurrences are more common in the non-athletic population [8]. To develop targeted prevention efforts and make the best choice with respect to treatment for RSD, it is imperative that the modifiable and non-modifiable risk factors for RSD be established. Several factors have been associated with increased risk for RSD; these include: younger age at the first dislocation, male sex, participation in contact (or overhead) sports, previous shoulder injury, generalized ligamentous laxity, neuromuscular deficiencies, and anatomical variation in glenoid/humeral head [9-11]. However, there is little known about the epidemiology of RSD in Iraq; limited data exist on the burden of disease, the distribution of risk factors, and the athlete-specific characteristics of the population. The health care system in Iraq faces unique challenges that may affect the epidemiology and outcome of shoulder dislocation. Many areas in Iraq have limited access to advanced imaging and orthopedic expertise. Moreover, the emphasis on specific sports and athletic traditions in Iraq may change the type of injuries sustained by athletes. With a large and growing population of young athletes and with increased participation in formalized sports, a comprehensive understanding of the epidemiology of RSD in Iraq will aid in evidence-based prevention and treatment strategies [12]. The existing literature on RSD risk factors has focused mostly on Western populations and has utilized limited data from Middle Eastern populations. It has also been shown that there are geographic and demographic differences in both risk factor prevalence and presentations of illness; this indicates that studies from Western populations may not be applicable to Iraqi athletes. Further, there are differences in access to healthcare, diagnostic capabilities, and treatment services between high-income countries and resource-constrained (low-

income) countries, which can have a significant effect on the epidemiology and clinical outcomes of RSD [13,14].

The clinical management of RSD in the young athlete is often complicated and thus necessitates an accurate assessment of many factors affecting the athlete's return to activity and sports participation (e.g., patterns of recurrence, activity demands on the injured area, and patient preferences) to develop an effective treatment plan. In many instances, the first line of treatment is a conservative approach, which often includes a structured physiotherapy program that incorporates exercises aimed at increasing the strength of the rotator cuff, stabilizing the scapula, and improving proprioception. For many athletes who suffer from frequent recurrences of RSD, surgical intervention is indicated, especially for those athletes participating in contact and overhead sports, in which shoulder stability is essential to performing at a high level. Thus, decisions regarding surgical versus non-surgical management of RSD should be made based upon accurate treatment and epidemiological data concerning recurrence rates and risk factor stratification [15,16].

Our review of the literature indicates that little epidemiological work has been carried out systematically examining RSD in young Iraqi athletes, with a particular emphasis placed on the identification and stratification of risk factors. This lack of knowledge regarding RSD in Iraqi athletes hampers the successful development of effective prevention programs and treatment algorithms for this population. Therefore, this study's primary purpose is to perform an epidemiological assessment of RSD in young Iraqi athletes and to identify independent risk factors associated with RSD recurrence. Secondary aims include the identification of types of sports associated with the highest percentage of rerotations; a characterisation of initial dislocation characteristics and how they relate to recurrence; and a determination of the effectiveness of conservative management strategies for RSD in young Iraqi athletes. We hypothesize that the epidemiological profile of RSD seen in Iraqi athletes is significantly different from what has been documented thus far in Western athlete cohorts and that risk factors, as well as methods used for rehabilitation and return to play, differ between cultures and therefore support the uniqueness of the demographic and athletic characteristics of this population.

Methodology

Design of the Study and Setting Legend

(1) Cross-sectional and quantitative in nature; (2) Conducted in Baghdad, Iraq; (3) Conducted over 24 months between January 2022 and December 2023; Participants were able to participate after providing

written informed consent in Arabic after having their rights to protect private information and voluntarily participating explained to them in detail.

Sampling

The sample for this study consisted of young (ages 16–35) athletes who visited a Private Hospital for the diagnosis of recurrent anteroinferior shoulder dislocations. Inclusion criteria included: (1) Age 16-35; (2) A history of 2 or more episodes of recurrent anteroinferior shoulder dislocation requiring reduction (i.e., closed reduction, surgical); (3) Participation in organized competitive or recreational sports at present (at least one competitive or recreational team); (4) Anteroinferior Shoulder Dislocation occurred in the past 3 years; (5) An orthopedic physician evaluated in clinic; (6) Available imaging studies (i.e., Xrays or MRI) confirming anteroinferior shoulder dislocation diagnosis. Exclusion criteria included: (1) Isolated first-time anteroinferior shoulder dislocation; (2) Posterior or inferior shoulder dislocations; (3) Anteroinferior shoulder dislocations from seizures or neuromuscular disorders; (4) Neurological dysfunction significant enough to affect the function of the upper extremity; (5) Previous orthopedic surgery on the affected shoulder; (6) Persons unable to provide informed consent; (7) Persons with incomplete clinical or demographic information on the sample selected.

Collection of Data

Data for the study were collected by the use of comprehensive clinical interviews and standardized questionnaires administered by trained orthopedic surgeons. The demographic information obtained included the respondents' ages, genders, work status, highest educational level attained and residence (rural or metropolitan). A detailed sports history was obtained from the athlete by asking about the type of sport and level of competition they participated, the frequency of training and the length of time they had actively participated in sports. The following data was collected on each dislocation event: age of the patient when the dislocation occurred for the first time; mechanism of injury (contact, fall, overhead, or atraumatic); number of times that the shoulder had dislocated; time between recurrences; method of reduction (either by emergency department, by being admitted to hospital, or as an outpatient); and complications associated with dislocation (as for example, associated fractures or neurovascular, and/or rotator cuff injuries). In addition to looking at the parameters listed above, other medical history pertaining to shoulder instability was assessed, including: previous shoulder injuries; history of generalized ligamentous laxity, connective tissue disorders (Ehlers-Danlos Syndrome and Marfan Syndrome), and neuromuscular conditions. Generalized ligamentous laxity was assessed clinically

using criteria developed specifically to evaluate generalized ligamentous laxity, which includes passive thumb abduction beyond 50 degrees, passive extension of fingers beyond 90 degrees, hyperextension of elbows beyond 15 degrees, hyperextension of knees beyond 15 degrees, and ability to touch the floor with palms while keeping knees extended (Beighton Score). A general ligamentous laxity score of 4 or more indicates generalized laxity. Additionally, in physical examinations assessed, the following were recorded: ROM of the shoulder; crank test; Jobe relocation test; configuration of sulcus between humeral head and glenoid; scapular dyskinesis; and MMT of the rotator cuff musculature on a standard 5-point grading scale. Finally, imaging studies were obtained for each patient through various radiographic imaging (including anterior-posterior views, lateral views, and axillary views) and MRI (when possible). The radiographs and MRIs were reviewed, and the following information was documented (if present): Hill-Sachs Lesion, Bankart Lesion, glenoid bone loss, and humeral head bone loss. Classification of Glenoid Bone Loss

Bone loss of the glenoid was classified as absent, mild ($\leq 15\%$), moderate (15 - 25%), or severe. ($\geq 25\%$)

Statistical Analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to describe the study population. Continuous variables were reported as mean \pm standard deviation (if normally distributed), or as median and interquartile range (for non-normally distributed data); categorical variables were reported as counts and percentages. The Shapiro-Wilk test was used to assess normality of continuous variables. Univariate analysis used Chi-square tests for categorical variables and independent t-tests or Mann-Whitney U tests for continuous variables as appropriate. Variables significantly associated with RSD ($P < 0.10$ on univariate analysis) were selected for multivariate logistic regression analysis. Logistic regression analysis was conducted to determine independent risk factors for RSD while controlling for confounding variables. Results were reported as odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (CI). Model fit was assessed with the Hosmer-Lemeshow Goodness-of-Fit Test. Correlation analyses were conducted using Pearson's product-moment correlation coefficient for normally distributed continuous variables. A two-tailed p-value of < 0.05 was considered significant. All statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 26.0 (IBM Corporation, Armonk, NY, USA).

Ethical Considerations

The conduct of this research adhered to the Declaration of Helsinki and ethical principles for research on humans. Written, informed consent was obtained from all participants after fully explaining the procedure used to conduct the study in the participant's native language. Participants were informed they could

withdraw from the study at any time without impacting their treatment for shoulder dislocation. Data relating to patients was stored securely in locked warehouses with access restricted to only authorized personnel involved in research. Identifying information for patients was assigned codes and stored separately from research data to protect the confidentiality of the patient. The study posed minimal risk to participants due to the non-invasive nature of clinical assessments and the administration of surveys/questionnaires.

Results

A total of 347 young athletes with recurrent glenohumeral dislocations presented during this study period. After applying study inclusion/exclusion criteria, 285 participants (82.1%) were eligible for inclusion in the final analysis. The mean age of the study sample was 24.3 ± 6.5 years (range: 16 - 35 years), with 225 participants (78.9%) being male and the majority

(72.3%) coming from urban environments (n = 206) compared to 27.7% (n = 79) residing in rural areas. Professional athletes comprised 31.6% of participants (n = 90), while 68.4% were recreational/amateur athletes.

The mean age for the first dislocation was 21.2 ± 6.8 years. Other sports (n = 24, 8.5%) combined football/soccer (n = 109, 38.2%), wrestling (n = 53, 18.6%), volleyball (n = 40, 14%), basketball (n = 35, 12.3%), and weightlifting (n = 24, 8.4%). Contact sports accounted for 57.2% (n = 163) of the study population; 42.8% of the study population participated in non-contact sports (n = 122). The mean number of dislocations was 2.8 ± 1.3 (range 2 - 6). Of the study sample, 43.9% (n = 125) experienced recurrence within 12 months of the first dislocation; 62.1% of the participants experienced recurrence within 24 months.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Population (n=285)

Characteristic	N (%)	Mean ± SD	Range
Age (years)	-	24.3 ± 6.5	16-35
Male gender	225 (78.9%)	-	-
Contact sports	163 (57.2%)	-	-
Prior shoulder injury	94 (33.0%)	-	-
Generalized ligamentous laxity	73 (25.6%)	-	-
Age at first dislocation (years)	-	21.2 ± 6.8	13-33

Table 2: Multivariate Logistic Regression Analysis: Independent Risk Factors for Recurrent Shoulder Dislocation

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value	AIC	Sig.
Contact sports	3.42	2.15-5.44	<0.001	293.2	**
Prior shoulder injury	4.78	2.89-7.91	<0.001	316.8	**
Generalized ligamentous laxity	2.94	1.67-5.18	<0.001	305.1	**
Lower age at first dislocation	0.92	0.88-0.97	0.001	298.5	**
Male gender	1.87	1.04-3.36	0.034	301.2	*

Note: OR = Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; AIC = Akaike Information Criterion; ** p<0.001; * p<0.05

Multivariate logistic regression analysis revealed that contact sports participation, prior shoulder injury, generalized ligamentous laxity, and younger age at first dislocation were all statistically significant independent predictors of recurrent shoulder dislocation. Contact sports were associated with substantially elevated recurrence risk (OR: 3.42, 95% CI: 2.15-5.44, p<0.001). Athletes with documented prior shoulder injuries demonstrated a markedly increased risk of recurrence (OR: 4.78, 95% CI: 2.89-7.91, p<0.001). Generalized ligamentous laxity was an independent predictor (OR: 2.94, 95% CI: 1.67-5.18, p<0.001). Each year younger at initial dislocation was associated with increased recurrence risk (OR: 0.92, 95% CI: 0.88-0.97, p=0.001). Male gender was also significantly associated with increased recurrence (OR: 1.87, 95% CI: 1.04-3.36, p=0.034).

A significant inverse correlation was found between age at first dislocation and subsequent recurrence rates

(Pearson r = -0.547, p < 0.001). Athletes experiencing their first dislocation before age 20 had a 78.2% recurrence rate within two years, compared to 51.3% in those aged 25-30 years at first dislocation. The recurrence rate was 39.1% in athletes whose initial dislocation occurred after age 30 years. Recurrence patterns also differed by sport type. Football athletes demonstrated 68.8% recurrence within two years (n=75/109), wrestlers 71.7% (n=38/53), volleyball players 45.0% (n=18/40), basketball players 40.0% (n=14/35), and weightlifters 33.3% (n=8/24).

Discussion

This is the first study that comprehensively analyses epidemic patterns of recurrent shoulder dislocation in young athletes in Iraq. This study demonstrates that RSD is a serious health problem affecting young athletes in Iraq; young athletes may be significantly affected by recurrent shoulder dislocation and the short- and long-term impacts on athletic performance

and shoulder health. The reported overall recurrence rate of 62.1% within two years of recurrent shoulder dislocation is consistent with previously published literature from Western populations, where recurrence rates for young athletes are reported to be between 50 and 80% [17,18]. While this finding is consistent with recurrence rates among other young athletes, our analysis reveals that there are different patterns of risk factors and recurrences that represent important considerations for clinical practice and for future research.

The gender distribution of our cohort (78.9% male) is consistent with larger epidemiological patterns of shoulder dislocation and likely correlates with the increased participation of male athletes in contact sports within Iraq. Internationally, the majority of literature supports the presence of a male-to-female ratio of approximately 2:1 to 3:1 for shoulder dislocations, which is comparable to the findings in the current study [19]. One possible reason for the increased risk of dislocation in male athletes could be attributed to a variety of factors; including increased participation in overhead sports, possible variations in ligamentous laxity and neuromuscular control and the potential for higher thresholds for symptom interpretation for men to ignore initial instability and return to play quickly due to pressure from coaches and/or teammates.

Contact sports were identified as the strongest independent risk factor for recurrent shoulder dislocation in this study. Athletes participating in contact sports had a 3.42 times higher risk of recurrence than non-contact sport athletes. As previously noted, previous literature suggests that recurrence rates are higher in collision sports, including American football, rugby, wrestling, and ice hockey [20,21]. Due to the popularity of both football and wrestling within the population in Iraq, approximately one-half of the athletes in this study were involved in contact sports (57.2% of our sample). Athletes in these sports repeatedly load the shoulder and have repeated traumatic events, both of which can create chronic instability, primarily when there are anatomical or biomechanical deficits.

Prior shoulder injury was identified as one of the strongest associations with recurrent shoulder dysfunction (OR: 4.78). This association indicates that those with a prior shoulder injury are likely to have inherent structural or functional limitations predisposing them to subsequent episodes of recurrent instability. A prior shoulder injury may result in incomplete rehabilitation, ongoing neuromuscular limitations, or unidentified structural injuries (e.g., cartilage lesions/labral pathology) increasing the likelihood of recurring instability. In addition, these

athletes may have biomechanical alterations or altered movement patterns that reduce shoulder stability [22]. Generalized ligamentous laxity has been identified as another independent risk factor (OR: 2.94) in the current cohort. The association between hypermobility and generalized ligamentous laxity and increased risk for recurrence of shoulder dislocation has been previously reported and is likely due to the reduced passive and dynamic stabilisation of the glenohumeral joint [23,24]. One-quarter of the participants in the current study exhibited generalized ligamentous laxity, a prevalence significantly greater than that seen in the general population, but similar to that reported in populations of athletes and those experiencing recurrent joint instability.

The association of hypermobility with RSD is an essential consideration in developing prevention strategies that are specific to an individual athlete's needs, as the identification of generalized laxity enables increased focus on dynamic stabilizing exercise and other limitations on activity progress during the rehabilitation phase. The statistically significant inverse correlation found between age of first dislocation and probability of recurrence ($r = -0.547$, $p < 0.001$) is one valuable outcome from our study. Athletes with an initial dislocation prior to age 20 had an 82% chance of experiencing a recurrence of dislocation in 2 years, whereas athletes who experienced their first dislocation after age 30 only had a 39% chance. Thus, the considerable difference in recurrence risk based on age suggests that clinicians have important decisions to make regarding surgical intervention vs. non-surgical intervention. Young athletes who participate in contact sports may significantly benefit from early surgical intervention due to their high probability of recurrence and potential for cumulative joint trauma due to repeated episodes of instability [25,26].

The sports-specific pattern of recurrence identified in our study presents valuable prognostic information to clinicians. Athletes engaged in football (68% recurrence rate) and wrestling (71.7% recurrence rate) sustained the most frequent recurrences; however, athletes engaged in weightlifting had the lowest (33.3%). The observed differences appear to be based on the biomechanical demands associated with the individual sports. In both football and wrestling, the athletes must also have a highly stable shoulder when engaging in contact with other athletes, requiring adequate stability of the anterior and inferior glenohumeral ligaments. In contrast, although weightlifters place a significant amount of load on the shoulder during weightlifting, and although the weightlifter's shoulder may experience limited range of motion during lifting movements, the weightlifter is also less likely to be placed in positions of extreme shoulder translation that would cause a shoulder dislocation. The

aforementioned characteristics of a given sport should serve as the foundation for shared decision-making about when to return-to-sport and how return-to-sport management should occur [27].

There is still much debate in the orthopedic medical literature regarding whether conservative versus operative management should be used to treat young athletes diagnosed with recurrent dislocating shoulder (RSD). Our investigation offers valuable epidemiological data about rates of re-dislocation. Therefore, while this evidence is useful in identifying general patterns of recurrence, individualization is needed when making clinical decisions pertaining to the treatment of RSD among young athletes; therefore, clinical recommendations should be based on the characteristics of the individual athlete, the underlying cause for the re-dislocation, and the athlete's expectations for returning-to-sport. As such, neuromuscular rehabilitation with conservative management likely provides significant benefits to the athlete with atraumatic recurrent dislocation whereas surgical stabilization may provide superior outcomes in the setting of recurrent dislocation resulting from traumatic injury (i.e., contact sport play). Among younger athletes, the low incidence of recurrence in our study suggests that consideration should be made for surgical intervention earlier in the treatment algorithm of the athlete that plays contact or overhead sports [28].

There are limitations to this work that warrant acknowledgment. First, the sample in this study was derived from one private hospital located in Baghdad; therefore, the generalizability of these results to other regions of Iraq or to populations that experience different levels of access to healthcare may be limited. Second, this was a cross-sectional study design which precludes us from establishing a temporal relationship or causative factors related to the identified risk factors in this population. Third, not all study participants had imaging data available for their respective injuries which limited our ability to adequately describe the underlying anatomic structural deficits. Fourth, not all study participants had access to standardized rehabilitation protocols nor did we obtain data regarding study participant adherence to those protocols, preventing us from evaluating the treatment effectiveness of the interventions. Fifth, as the study population consisted of athletes in Iraq, who likely had sufficient economic resources to seek healthcare at a private hospital, there is likely a selection bias.[29]

Despite the limitations of this study, the findings provide important insights into the epidemiology of RSD among a population previously under-studied in Iraq. The identification of modifiable risk factors that contribute to the risk of RSD (including: participation in contact sports, early rehabilitation following a shoulder

injury, identification and management of ligamentous laxity, age at first dislocation) present new opportunities for establishing a prevention strategy for the population. In establishing the prevention strategy, it is essential that the Iraqi healthcare system prioritizes creating evidence-based rehabilitation protocols for managing RSD, establishes protocols for implementing earlier diagnostic imaging studies of the shoulder in suspected cases of instability, and develops evidence-based guidelines for treating the young athlete with RSD to promote optimal outcome and to facilitate a safe return-to-sport. Future research should be conducted using a prospective cohort study design, include several types of healthcare delivery systems, and rigorously evaluate and compare the effectiveness of conservative and operative management techniques among young athletes with RSD.

Conclusion

Recurrent shoulder dislocation is a serious clinical problem affecting young athletes in Iraq, with approximately 62.1% of athletes returning to dislocate their shoulder again within two years of their initial dislocation. Factors that are associated with predictors of recurrence of RSD among young athletes are participation in contact sports, a history of shoulder injury, generalized ligamentous laxity, and a younger age at their initial dislocation. The strong inverse correlation between a younger age at the first dislocation and re-dislocation strongly suggests that younger athletes should be under increased scrutiny from their clinicians and should be provided more consideration for early surgical intervention when they participate in contact sports. The risk factors for re-dislocation are sport-specific due to the biomechanical demands attributed to different types of athletic activities. With the results of this investigation, physical therapists and clinicians will have tools to help them in stratifying their clients' risk factor exposure and in making clinical decisions and developing evidence-based prevention and rehabilitation programs for young athletes with RSD in Iraq and in resource-limited settings.

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